

INTERPRETABLE PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF CHARACTER EXPRESSION IN FRENCH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: In this article, phraseological units that express the character of a person in French and Uzbek have been studied in a comparative aspect. It is not in vain that a small layer of phraseological systems associated with human character is taken for research. Phraseological units expressing the character of a person make it possible to identify linguistic and extra linguistic connections between two languages. According to the results of studies conducted in two languages, the structure and semantics of phraseological units representing the character of a person were divided into certain types. Thematic units are collected from phraseological dictionaries and their lexicographic nature is studied.

Key words: Phraseological equivalents, inter linguistically, functional-stylistic, phraseological analogues

The problem of determining the main criteria of whether a certain phraseological unit belongs to full or partial equivalents is one of the important issues of modern phraseology. It should be noted that there are certain differences in defining the types of inter linguistic phraseological equivalence relations. In our research, the cross-study of phraseological units in French and Uzbek languages is aimed at identifying and studying allomorphic and isomorphic features at the phraseological level, complete and partial equivalents and analogs in the two languages, non-equivalent phraseological units that do not match in the phraseological system of another language.

First of all, it is necessary to note certain inconsistencies in the terminological definition of the types of inter linguistic relations. Together with the concepts of "equivalent" and "analogue", a number of authors have defined "identification", "lexical variation or structural synonymy", "ideographic synonymy", "hyper-hyponymy", "stylistic synonymy", "homonymy and polysemy" [5], "identical similarities" and "partial similarities" [7], "semantic-component correspondences", "semantically equal units" and "semantically distinct units", "absolutely identical" and "semantically identical FB" [1], they use the symbols "inter lingually similar FB", "idiomatic compatibility", which in turn makes it difficult to solve the problem. On the other hand, the determination of different aspects of the correspondence of phraseological units in different languages by different researchers leads to a certain uncertainty of

the definitions of phraseological equivalents and analogues. Thus, taking into account the phraseological equivalents of sister languages, L. Mironyuk defines phraseological units based on the same vocabulary, the same main word, but different components, different core words, the same components and different vocabulary content [3]. The scientist calls FB in different languages corresponding to the main semantic components of equivalence as phraseological equivalence according to the interdependence of imagery, stylistic coloring, lexical and structural-grammatical content. According to him, analogues are semantically the same, but differ in structure according to the underlying image, that is, not only the denotative aspect of the meaning of the foreign language phraseological unit, but also its expressive-emotional connotation and functional-stylistic features are formed. According to A.Narzikulov, phraseological units whose meaning and lexical structure are fully or partially consistent and perform the same stylistic function are called phraseological equivalents, phraseological analogues - differ in terms of lexical structure, express a similar meaning, perform the same stylistic function, and sometimes the phrase corresponds to one of the components are expressions [4]. M.I. Umarchodzhayev distinguishes stable compounds whose meaning is compatible in two languages as phraseological equivalents [8]. According to G.Salomov's definition, phraseological units that correspond to each other in two or more languages can be considered equivalent, regardless of the context. They also include phraseological units borrowed from other languages. Phraseological units that correspond to each other only in certain contexts belong to the class of analogs [6]. Thus, even a simple enumeration of the criteria for determining phraseological equivalents and analogs in the works of linguists-scientists reveals a typical picture of very important inconsistencies in their definition. At the same time, in the framework of this research, other researchers have also conducted research. R. Zorivchak in his candidate's dissertation understands full equivalence as the same subject-logical content, structural-grammatical content, same concrete/denotative/imagery and similar functional-stylistic and expressive emotional meanings. Analyzing a large number of factual materials, the author identifies full and partial phraseological equivalents and shows the possibility of restoring complete adequacy in translation.

D. Kvesevich distinguishes full and partial phraseological equivalents, defining the first as phraseological units compatible with components, meaning, image and grammatical structure, and partial equivalents as phraseological units with only minor lexical or grammatical differences. According to him, analog is

adequate in its meaning, but differs in its components. There is no more complex problem in linguistics than the problem of meaning, and the meaning of phraseological idioms is multifaceted, and researchers have not yet come to a single opinion on the issues of its study. Due to the complexity of the semantics of phraseological units, the system of cross-linguistic phraseological equivalence seems to be quite complex. When working out the problem of cross-linguistic phraseological equivalence, many linguists proposed to consider the following as the most important signs of phraseological meaning: semantic, structural-grammatical, component, significant-denotative, subjective-evaluative, functional-stylistic, connotative (emotionally expressive), oboist- are associative (internal form) signs. However, whatever symbols are proposed, cross-linguistic phraseological equivalence systems are usually divided into the following classifications: 1) phraseological equivalents (complete, partial, etc.), 2) phraseological analogues (representing close or approximate similarity) and 3) non-equivalent phraseological units [2] . The analysis of scientific sources on this issue shows that the problem of identifying and studying phraseological equivalents and analogues is urgent, complex and multifaceted, and requires a clear approach to its solution and, first of all, the development of criteria for determining phraseological equivalence. So, the signs of FB can be considered in three aspects: 1. Studying the semantic level of phraseological units; 2. Considering the structural and grammatical level of the studied material; 3. Component level. The semantic level of the research is aimed at identifying the semantic features of similarities and differences between French and Uzbek phraseological units. This aspect is the main decisive factor in distinguishing between allomorphic and isomorphic phenomena. At the semantic level, we distinguish the significant-denotative, subjective-evaluative meaning of FB, the functional-stylistic and emotional-expressive connotations of phraseological units. In distinguishing phraseological equivalents and analogues, the comparison of the schemes of different phraseological units is of great importance. The structural-grammatical level includes the comparison of the structural models of the FB based on the structural models of free phrases specific to both languages and specific to each of the compared languages, as well as the possibility of adequately replacing the structural-grammatical differences specific to each of the compared languages. The component level involves the identification of elements of the same, semantically similar or different types in the composition of the compared phraseology. This level is the

most common and specific units for FB of both languages. Taking into account these levels, we distinguished the following types of inter linguistic relations:

1. Phraseological equivalents / complete and partial/. 2. Phraseological analogues / complete and partial/. 3. Non-equivalent phraseological units. We will consider each of the selected types separately. Multilingual phraseological equivalents include FBs that have the same semantics, structural-grammatical structure, and component composition. As a result of the analysis of phraseological units expressing personality in French and Uzbek languages, pairs of inter linguistically equivalent phraseology were identified.

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